

Harmful phytoplankton species in coastal and deep waters around Cozumel, Mexican Caribbean

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Abstract

The distribution and abundance of harmful algal blooms (HABs) species is influenced by biotic and abiotic characteristics of the ecosystem. Here, we studied the relationship between harmful bloom forming phytoplankton species and physicochemical and hydrological factors in the Mexican Caribbean. Samplings were performed in oceanic (0 - 200 m depth; daytime) and coastal (0 - 20 m depth; circadian cycles) waters to the east and west of Cozumel Island at different depth layers. The phytoplankton community was dominated by the nitrogen-fixing cyanobacteria *Trichodesmium* spp. In the oceanic region, the highest densities of HABs species *Alexandrium* spp. (2,111 cells L⁻¹), *Phalacroma rotundatum* (56 cells L⁻¹), *Karenia* sp. (333 cells L⁻¹), *Prorocentrum lima* (56 cells L⁻¹), and *Prorocentrum rhathymum* (56 cells L⁻¹) were recorded in the mixed layer: at the surface and the maximum chl *a* fluorescence layer, associated with high temperature, lower salinity, and low nutrient concentrations. In the coastal zone, where reduce depth favors mixing and resuspension processes, the benthic species *Gambierdiscus* sp. was also recorded. The highest densities of the HABs species *Alexandrium* sp. (200 cells L⁻¹), *Gambierdiscus* sp. (40 cells L⁻¹) and *Phalacroma rotundatum* (40 cells L⁻¹) occurred during both day and night; for *Karenia* sp. (60 cells L⁻¹) and *Prorocentrum lima* (60 cells L⁻¹) only during the night, and for *Prorocentrum rhathymum* only during the day, seemingly related to variations in the phosphorous nutrients.

Keywords: phytoplankton ecology, diatoms, dinoflagellates, circadian cycles, stratification

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Introduction

The frequency of occurrence of harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the Caribbean Sea has increased according to records from 1985 to 2018 (Hallegraeff *et al.*, 2021). Globally, it is one of the regions with the highest recurrence of intoxications associated with toxic phytoplankton due to the presence of ciguatoxins in fish, which when consumed by humans, cause ciguatera illness (Hallegraeff *et al.*, 2021; Sunesen *et al.*, 2021). Besides ciguatera, different types of intoxications have been recorded in the region, such as those produced by paralytic shellfish toxins (PST) and neurotoxic shellfish toxins (NST) (Sunesen *et al.*, 2021).

In the Mexican Caribbean the dinoflagellate *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *bahamense* stands out as an important HAB species, forming blooms with high densities in coastal lagoons (Gómez-Aguirre, 1998). Recent works have recognized the presence of different bloom-forming species, especially benthic dinoflagellates associated with macroalgae. Among such species, *Gambierdiscus/Fukuyoa*, *Ostreopsis*, *Amphidinium*, *Prorocentrum* and *Coolia* stand out (Almazán-Becerril *et al.*, 2015; Durán-Riveroll *et al.*, 2019; Tarazona-Janampa *et al.*, 2020). However, knowledge of the environmental factors that are associated with HAB-forming species is scarce.

Oceanic and coastal environments are contrasting, mainly due to the bathymetric differences between them. These differences modify the physical and chemical characteristics of the water that regulate the growth and distribution of phytoplankton (Whitney *et al.*, 2005), including harmful

and/or toxic phytoplankton. In oceanic zones, outside the continental shelf, characterized by deep waters, the distribution of planktonic communities is mainly associated with mesoscale physical processes influenced by differences in water density (Mena *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, in the shallow coastal zone, the distribution of phytoplankton communities is associated in the short-term with tidal variation, light and wind intensity.

In this study, we aimed to analyze the relationship between HAB-forming phytoplankton species and physical, chemical, and hydrological factors in the Mexican Caribbean. For this purpose, we used physico-chemical and biological information collected in the oceanic and coastal waters around Cozumel Island.

Material and Methods

Study area

Cozumel Island is located in the east of the Yucatan Peninsula, SE Mexico (Fig. 1). The region has a humid subtropical climate with a rainy season between June and October, a cold front season between November and February, and a warm and dry season between March and May.

The Cozumel Island opens to the Caribbean Sea with depths greater than 1000 m to the east, while to the west, the Island and the Yucatan Peninsula are separated by the narrow (approx. 18 km wide), relatively deep (400 m depth) Cozumel Channel (CC). Cozumel has a semidiurnal micro-tidal regime (range ~0.2 m), and is influenced by a strong western boundary current (Yucatan

current) which flows persistently northward around the island.

Fig. 1. Study area showing the oceanic stations (black squares) and the coastal sampling point (red square).

Sampling and in situ measurements

Two sampling strategies were used to obtain information on the variation of HAB-forming species and associated environmental factors in the waters around Cozumel Island.

In the oceanic environment, an oceanographic survey on board the R/V Justo Sierra was carried out in April/May 2019 (dry season). Fourteen stations distributed on both sides of Cozumel Island were visited. At each station, three depth strata were sampled: surface (< 10 m), chl *a* fluorescence maximum (62-96 m) and the halocline (96-151 m).

In the coastal zone, a fixed sampling point was established at ~25 m bottom depth, and two 48 h sampling cycles were carried out: one in Sept/Oct 2020 (rainy season) and the other in Apr 2021 (dry season). In each sampling cycle, samples were taken every 4 h at the surface and at 20 m depth.

Water temperature, salinity and density values were recorded *in situ* using a Seabird 9 CTD probe in the oceanic environment, or a SWIFT SVP CTD profiler in the coastal zone. At each sampling depth, both in the oceanic and coastal environment, water samples (250-500 mL) were taken and fixed with Lugols solution to estimate phytoplankton density (Thronsdon, 1978). Water samples (2-3 L) were obtained to estimate the concentration of chl-*a* and nutrients, which were refrigerated until they were transferred to the laboratory.

Phytoplankton, nutrients, and chlorophyll-a
Samples for quantitative analysis of phytoplankton were placed in sedimentation chambers and species composition and abundance were estimated following the Utermöhl method (Hasle, 1978). The refrigerated water samples were filtered through 0.45 μm membranes, which were used to estimate the chl *a* concentration following the trichromatic method (Aminot and Rey, 2000). The filtered water was used to estimate the concentration of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN: ammonium + nitrites + nitrates) and dissolved inorganic phosphorous (DIP) according to colorimetric methods (Strickland and Parsons, 1970).

Results and Discussion

In both the oceanic and coastal zones, the highest phytoplankton densities were of the cyanobacteria *Trichodesmium* spp. Despite this cyanobacterium being the cause of HABs in other parts of the world, in the Caribbean it is considered a resident species and of particular importance in this oligotrophic region, due to the atmospheric nitrogen fixation it performs (Bergman *et al.*, 2013).

In the oceanic region, 70 phytoplankton species were recorded, of which five were HAB-species and occurred at low densities (Table 1). *Alexandrium* sp. was the most abundant taxon, followed by *Karenia*, *Prorocentrum rhathymum*, *Prorocentrum lima* and *Phalacroma rotundatum*. These dinoflagellates were recorded in the surface and Chl *a* fluorescence maximum layer, which had high temperature (26.1-27.8 °C), low salinity (36.2-36.5) and low concentration of nitrogenous and phosphate nutrients. Instead, the halocline layer had the highest nutrient concentrations, but low phytoplankton biomass (Fig. 2). Such results suggest that the stratification in the water column plays some role in defining the vertical distribution of the HAB-forming species.

In the coastal zone, 113 phytoplankton species were recorded, of which six were HAB-forming species: the same taxa as in the oceanic zone, plus the benthic dinoflagellate *Gambierdiscus* sp. (Table 1). Resuspension of this species is likely associated with the greater interaction of water fluxes (e.g. tidal waves, and their associated currents or wind waves, among others) with the seabed in this shallow area. The HABs species *Alexandrium*,

Table 1. Maximum cell abundances of HAB forming species in the oceanic (dry season, 2019) and coastal zone (dry season 2020 and rainy season 2021) of the waters around Cozumel Island (in cells L⁻¹).

Species	Oceanic zone	Coastal zone	MPL
<i>Alexandrium</i> sp.	2111	200	1000
<i>Phalacroma rotundatum</i>	56	40	200*
<i>Karenia</i> sp.	333	60	5000**
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>	56	60	200
<i>Prorocentrum rhathymum</i>	60	40	200***
<i>Gambierdiscus</i> sp.	-	40	

MPL, maximum permissible limit according to COFEPRIS in Mexico. *Considering the genus *Dinophysis*, ***Karenia brevis* and ****Prorocentrum lima* as a reference.

Gambierdiscus sp., and *P. rotundatum* were recorded during both day and night. *Karenia* sp. and *P. lima* were recorded only during night time, and *P. rhathymum* only during day time, coinciding with the maximum DIP (Fig. 2). HABs species densities at different times of the day suggest a relationship with diel variation in nitrogen and phosphorous nutrients.

The presence in low densities of *P. rotundatum* and *P. lima* in the region suggests a potential risk for diarrheic intoxications (DSP) in the study area.

Fig. 2. Average concentration of the dissolved inorganic nitrogen (a), dissolved inorganic phosphorous (b), and Chl *a* (c) in different depths in the oceanic and coastal zone of the waters around Cozumel Island. Surf., surface; Max-FI, maximum of fluorescence; Halocl., halocline; SD, surface daytime; SN, surface nighttime; 20 mD, 20 m depth daytime; 20 mN, 20 m depth nighttime.

Alexandrium was the most abundant bloom-forming dinoflagellate both in the oceanic and the coastal zone. Yet, its density was almost ten times higher in the open sea. According to the guidelines of the Federal Committee for Protection from Sanitary Risks (COFEPRIS, 2016), the maximum

permissible limit in Mexico for the genus *Alexandrium* in seawater is 1,000 cells L⁻¹ (Table 1). Therefore, at least in the oceanic environment, it can be considered that there is a risk for paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP).

Our results suggest that vertical variation in physical and chemical factors and bathymetric characteristics control the distribution of HAB-forming species at different spatial and temporal scales. Stratification seems to control the vertical distribution of HABs species in the epipelagic zone. In coastal areas, the low water depth and the variations in nutrients availability seem to influence the species composition.

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